

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

101035819

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
8	8.1	D36	Web-based repository and tool for mutual learning on R&I Impact	UPV/EHU

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	

Description (short)
<p>This deliverable presents a web-based tool which acts as a repository of international good practices on research impact assessment and measurement. The Deliverable describes the process leading to the repository set-up, covering the web-based tool development, the generation of contents and resources identification, as well as future steps.</p> <p>The repository brings together in a single place good practices of impact assessment and measurement, both in the context of ENLIGHT Universities and worldwide. It is expected to allow mutual learning on research impact by enabling open debate and discussion between ENLIGHT university academics and staff, and also external experts. As such, it will help ENLIGHT universities to raise impact awareness, to acquire impact literacy and to develop impact readiness, contributing thus to promote a culture of impact both within and beyond ENLIGHT.</p> <p>The web-based tool is available at this link impact.enlight-eu.org and is expected to be a live platform which is updated on a six-monthly basis.</p>

Document Version Control		
Version 0.1	Originated by	UPV/EHU, NUIG, UGENT
Version 0.2	Reviewed by	UGENT, UPV/EHU
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10404462	

The content of this deliverable represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains."

CONTENT TABLE

CONTENT TABLE	2
INTRODUCTION	3
<i>ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT RISE</i>	3
<i>The Repository of Good Practices on Research Impact</i>	3
1. THE PROCESS	5
1.1. <i>Content Development</i>	5
1.1.1 Review and analysis phase	5
1.1.2. Repository structure and proposal of contents	7
1.2. <i>Web-based tool development</i>	9
2. REPOSITORY CONTENT	10
2.1. <i>Landing Page</i>	10
2.2. <i>Understanding Research Impact</i>	12
2.3. <i>Policy Frameworks for Research Impact</i>	14
2.4. <i>Higher Education Policies for Research Impact</i>	16
2.5. <i>Methodologies for Research Impact</i>	19
2.6. <i>Our Research Impact Team</i>	23
3. THE WEB-BASED TOOL	25

INTRODUCTION

ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT RISE

ENLIGHT is a European University Alliance to promote equitable quality of life, sustainability and global engagement through Higher Education Transformation. ENLIGHT brings together nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries (University of the Basque Country, University of Bordeaux, Comenius University Bratislava, National University Ireland Galway, Ghent University, University of Göttingen, University of Groningen, University of Tartu, Uppsala University).

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Programme and more specifically within the Science With and For Society (SWAFS) Work Programme. The **ENLIGHT RISE project** (Research and Innovation agenda with and for society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT Alliance. In synergy with ENLIGHT's educational components and surrounding ecosystems, ENLIGHT RISE will deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda for our universities.

The ENLIGHT RISE project is structured around nine major Work Packages, of which Work Package (WP) 8 is focused on Impact. **The main objective of WP8 is to promote a mission and impact-driven research and innovation agenda.** On the one hand WP8 is exploring the frontiers of a common impact-driven R&I agenda (task 8.1), by: analyzing the opportunities and barriers encountered to implement this agenda (8.1.3); developing actions to promote a culture of R&I impact (8.1.1); and by reviewing methods and good practices of impact assessment and measurement worldwide (8.1.2). On the other hand, it is sharing intelligence with other European Universities alliances as part of the FOREU2 initiative, to spread and share solutions, successful practices, identified barriers and challenges, as well as cooperation formats and models (Task 8.2).

In order to have a common ground to develop its activities, WP8 has decided to focus on the concept of "Research Impact", in alternative to R&I impact. It defines research impact as the effects of research in the real world. Impact is the changes we can see (demonstrate, measure, capture), beyond academia (in society, economy, environment) which happen because of our research (caused by, contributed to, attributable to).

The Repository of Good Practices on Research Impact

In alignment with the above-mentioned objectives, and more specifically the sub-task 8.1.2 objective of reviewing methods and good practices of impact assessment and measurement worldwide, this document presents the **web-based tool which is acting as a repository of international good practices on research impact assessment and measurement.**

The repository brings together in a single place good practices of impact assessment and measurement, both in the context of ENLIGHT Universities and worldwide. It is expected to

allow mutual learning on research impact by enabling open debate and discussion between ENLIGHT university academics and staff, and also external experts. As such, it will help ENLIGHT universities to raise impact awareness, to acquire impact literacy and to develop impact readiness, contributing thus to promote a culture of impact both within and beyond ENLIGHT.

The repository is therefore strongly linked with other WP8 sub-tasks (mainly 8.1.1 and 8.2), but also with other ENLIGHT RISE Work Packages. More concretely, the new web-based tool will be part of **WP2 ENLIGHT R&I Observatory** and it is accessible through the [Research & Innovation section of the ENLIGHT website](#), which has been developed in the framework of WP9. Likewise, the repository is also strongly linked with the impact-related work carried out in the framework of the Erasmus+ project, notably the development of a methodology and a toolkit for assessing the “long-term impact of ENLIGHT on people, communities, institutions, and systems at large”.

The repository is **open** to the overall public and should be seen as a **living tool** to be permanently nourished with the different guidelines, studies, analysis, tutorials and other reference sources allowing the ENLIGHT community and all interested experts to advance in their understanding, knowledge and work on research impact.

All resources included in the repository should be seen and understood in their specific academic, scientific, regional and historical context. There are no “*one size fits for all*” solutions and perfect methodologies, approaches, policy frameworks or strategic plans to promote research impact.

This document is organized in three main parts:

1. Chapter 1 describes the process leading to the repository set-up, including the development of the web-based tool, the generation of contents and resources identification;
2. Chapter 2 presents the content of the repository, its different sections and the main resources identified;
3. Chapter 3 introduces the web-based tool, how to get access to it and what it looks like.

1. THE PROCESS

The development of the repository of international good practices on research impact goes back to the first months of ENLIGHT RISE and the first meetings of Work Package 8 team, which is led by the University of the Basque Country, National University Ireland Galway and Ghent University, and made up of representatives of all 9 ENLIGHT Universities. In those first meetings of Autumn 2021, the WP8 team agreed that the repository development should encompass two major dimensions:

1. Review and analysis of good practices of impact assessment and measurement both worldwide and in the context of ENLIGHT;
2. Development of the web-based tool to be done in conjunction with the development WP2 ENLIGHT R&I Observatory and ENLIGHT website.

1.1. Content Development

1.1.1 Review and analysis phase

As a departing point, the WP8 team agreed to make a **first review and analysis of already existing repositories on impact**. The objective was to avoid duplicating already existing work, to get inspiration and to build-upon successful repositories, whilst answering the specific needs of ENLIGHT repository target groups. During this exploratory phase, the analysis went beyond the specifics of research impact and covered also other fields, such as impact of economic activities or policies.

WP8 analysis of existing impact-related repositories helped identify good examples of repositories and elements to be taken into account in the ENLIGHT one. Figure 1 shows the 26 repositories and resources related to impact assessment and measurement that have been carefully analyzed by WP8 in this preliminary phase of the ENLIGHT repository development. They were classified as:

- *Repositories gathering examples of research projects and initiatives*, such as the Social Impact Open Repository (SIOR), the REF Impact Case Studies (UK) or the Horizon Results Platform;
- Repositories including a catalog of metrics (e.g. IRIS Catalog of Metrics);
- Repositories including impact assessment approaches and methodologies (e.g. Europeana Impact Playbook, Global Database for Regulatory Impact Assessment);
- Repositories including training modules and materials on research impact (e.g. Parthenos, The International School of Research Impact Assessment);
- Toolkits, such as the UKRI Impact toolkit for economic and social sciences; and
- Repositories combining several types of content.

Repository of Good Practices – 1) ANALYSIS of ADDITIONAL REPOSITORIES / RESOURCES						
Content	Sources					
Examples of Impactful R&I projects/initiatives (& Impact Assessment approaches/ methodologies)	SIOR (Social Impact Open Repository) (ES)	REF Impact Case Studies (UK)	Northern Knowledge Stories (NL)	IDB Impact Evaluations Repository	Horizon Results Platform	Multiple Individual Universities repositories of case studies
Catalogue of metrics	IRIS Catalog of Metrics					
Impact Assessment Approaches/ Methodologies	EUROPEANA IMPACT PLAYBOOK (step by step approach to help design, measure and narrate impact)	The International School of Research Impact Assessment Training materials on IA	Matter of Focus (commercial) Training resources on IA	Global Database for Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA) (World Bank) Examples of Governmental IA Methodologies		
Training sources	Parthenos (training modules about research impact)			Valorisation (Rathenau Institut) (article with links to definition, examples & valorisation guiding principles)		
Toolkits	UKRI Impact toolkit for economic and social sciences	UCD Research Impact Toolkit				
Combining several types of content	RRI Tools (tools for RRI, inspiring practices, projects and library elements; focus on ethics, gender equality, governance, open access science, public engagement, science education)	ACCOMPLISH Project (guides to impact planning, co-creation, impact assessment)	Research Impact Canada (case studies, blog, guidelines and toolkits)	Advancing Research Impact in Society – Resources (USA) (mix of resources)	Social Value UK (library, reports database, guidance, tools and tools by principle on Social Value approaches)	CampusEngage (Ireland) (Tools & publications; case studies; training actions; glossary of terms for societal engagement)
	Fast Track Impact (commercial) Very comprehensive and user friendly repository with guides, tools, training, IA)	Emerald Publishing-Real Impact (impact case studies & guides)	LSE Impact Blog (Blog with studies and resources)	Veriplo Ventures (commercial) IA methodology (ImpactTracker), case studies, national assessments, etc.	Research to Action: the Global Guide to Research Impact Comprehensive guidance on research impact (incl on ToC, measurement)	ASIRPA (training, case studies and publications on the societal impact of research)

Figure 1: Analysis of relevant Impact repositories and resources

In parallel to this review and analysis, and in conjunction with Task 8.1.3 (Collect and analyze opportunities and barriers encountered to implement a common impact-driven R&I agenda), WP8 has carried out a **Research Impact Landscaping exercise** across all 9 ENLIGHT Universities. Each ENLIGHT University was invited to answer 3 main questions:

1. What is your understanding of R&I Impact?
2. Does your University have a R&I Impact policy/ implementation plan? If so, could you please give more information about it?
3. Independently of the response to the previous question, could you please identify (a) good R&I Impact practice(s) in your University?

The landscaping exercise helped not only to get a brief overview of how research impact is dealt with at each ENLIGHT University, but also to identify good research impact practices to feed into the repository. During this exercise, it was made clear the importance of understanding and redefining the meaning of research impact since the concept's interpretation may lead to different types of responses and the identification of practices that deviate from the WP8's definition.

During this phase, the WP8 members also identified the **main users and target groups** of the future repository, more specifically the following players:

- Researchers;
- Research Support Staff;
- Impact Policy Managers;

- Universities' Management Teams (responsible for or planning to develop research impact agendas).

Even if at the moment of the project proposal the repository was planned to be confidential and access to be given only to the ENLIGHT community, WP8 agreed to make the web-based tool open and of public access to all interested users. Behind this decision is the fact that the resources are all of public nature, use and interest.

During this review and analysis phase, the WP8 members also agreed that the proposal reference to “best practice” should be redefined and replaced by “good practice” as the team is not making a comparative analysis and what is proven to be the “best” option in one specific context is not necessarily the “best” in another. It was agreed to avoid standardized “model” practices and include highly diversified practices, with a view to making the repository more inclusive than normative.

1.1.2. Repository structure and proposal of contents

As a result of the review and analysis phase, the WP8 leading team has proposed to organize the repository of good practices on research impact around 7 major sections:

1. Home area, where the main navigation map is presented;
2. About us;
3. Understanding Research impact;
4. Policy frameworks for promoting, assessing and/or funding research impact;
5. Universities Research impact-driven policies, strategies and/or plans;
6. Methodologies for Impact measurement and assessment; and
7. Research impact experts.

The detailed structure of the repository was further detailed and the interest of each section for the above-mentioned target groups identified. Figure 2 provides an overview of the objectives and structure of each section, the main target groups and the allocation of work amongst the WP8 leadership team. As it can be seen in this figure, apart from sections 1 (Home), 2 (About us), and 7 (Experts), all other sections are structured in a similar logic, including an introductory text and a main resources section.

Repository of Good Practices – CONTENT DEVELOPMENT (1/2)

PROPOSAL for CONTENTS

Section	Target Group	Co-leaders Responsibility
1. HOME <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scheme for repository navigation Logos of ENLIGHT, Project partners, EU funding Links to sections "about us" and "contact us" 	All	UPV/EHU
2. ABOUT US <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to ENLIGHT, RISE, WP8 & Repository Objectives Contact us 	All	UPV/EHU
3. UNDERSTANDING RESEARCH IMPACT WHAT IS RESEARCH IMPACT? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introductory text: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reference to the fact that there are different definitions of research impact (Scientific/ academic impact; Societal impact, including economic, political, environmental, technological, etc.; Impact vs "Valorization"; Different from knowledge exchange and transfer; Different from societal engagement). ENLIGHT definition. Sources (links to webpages, documents, video tutorials) 	Researchers Impact Policy Managers	UGENT
4. POLICY FRAMEWORKS FOR RESEARCH IMPACT WHAT POLICIES EXIST TO PROMOTE RESEARCH IMPACT? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introductory text (reference to the multiple approaches and levels of support to promote, fund and assess research impact) Sources: EU level/ European countries and regions/ International organisations/ Non-European countries 	Research Managers Researchers	UGENT

Repository of Good Practices – CONTENT DEVELOPMENT (2/2)

PROPOSAL for CONTENTS

Section	Target Group	Co-leaders Responsibility
5. HEIs POLICIES FOR RESEARCH IMPACT WHAT ARE HEIs DOING TO PROMOTE RESEARCH IMPACT? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introductory text : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reference to the multiple approaches followed by the different HEIs (context-dependent) Reference to guidelines (and future ENLIGHT toolkit) for Impact Literacy Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Impact at ENLIGHT Universities. Research Impact at other European/ Non-European Universities HEIs Impact Literacy Guidelines 	Universities' Management teams Impact Policy Managers Research managers	NUIG
6. METHODOLOGIES FOR RESEARCH IMPACT HOW CAN I PLAN, ASSESS and MEASURE RESEARCH IMPACT? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introductory text: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain the structure of the section: planning, assessing/measuring and communicating Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact planning (Theory of change impact pathways, impact planning canvas, ...) Impact measurement and assessment (experimental versus non-experimental approaches...) Examples of case studies of impactful research (SIOR, REF and other repositories of case studies) 	Researchers Impact Policy Managers	NUIG
7. WHO CAN I CONTACT FOR SUPPORT? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introductory text Contact boxes organised by ENLIGHT University 	All	UPV/EHU

Figure 2: Structure of the ENLIGHT repository of good practices on research impact

On the basis of the agreed repository structure, the three WP8 leading partners (UPV/EHU, NUIG, UGENT) started working on a common document where the introductory texts were developed and the main resources identified. The consistency between the different sections and review of all the provided input was done by the WP8 leader (UPV/EHU). The WP8

members were invited to support the leadership team in the identification of resources to feed the repository.

1.2. Web-based tool development

In parallel to the process of developing the content of the repository, the WP8 leading team has launched the different measures to set up the web-based tool, which acts as the actual repository of good practices on research impact.

The first question to be answered was about where to locate the web-based tool. The WP8 leading team had several interactions with both WP2 leaders who are responsible for the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory and WP9 communication task leaders in charge of the ENLIGHT public website.

In relation to the **R&I Observatory** it was mentioned that both tools pursue different, but complementary objectives. The WP8 repository consists of a collection of good practices of impact assessment and measurement, both in the context of ENLIGHT Universities and worldwide; and WP2 R&I Observatory consists of “an online one-stop shop portal centralizing various benchmarking results, surveys, and evidence-based policy recommendations emerging from the project”. In that context, it was agreed that the tools should be developed in parallel and a link to WP8 repository should be included in the R&I Observatory.

Concerning the links with **WP9 communication** related tasks, and because of the absence of a common ENLIGHT server, WP8 was suggested to develop and host the repository web-based tool in the context of the leading partner server, in this case the UPV/EHU's one. For that purpose, UPV/EHU hired the services of an external web developer provider, in alignment with the ENLIGHT RISE grant agreement and the University subcontracting rules.

Access to the repository of good practices on research impact will be also given through the ENLIGHT website, in particular under the Research & Innovation heading. The objective is that there is the same “ENLIGHT look and feel” when navigating in the repository web-based tool. For that purpose, ENLIGHT branding guidelines were duly followed and respected. Besides, the WP8 team reviewed some of the initial content sections (e.g. “home”, “about us”, “contact us”) to give users the perception that they are still navigating in the ENLIGHT website.

With all these issues clarified, the web-based tool was developed in three main sequential phases: 1/ webpage design (colors, pictures, text formats, icons, etc.); 2/ webpage development and content uploading; and 3/ testing and refinements.

2. REPOSITORY CONTENT

In this section we present the contents of the repository of good practices on research impact as published on the 19th of August 2022. As previously mentioned at the introduction of this deliverable, the repository should be considered as a living tool to be permanently nourished with the different resources allowing the ENLIGHT community and all interested experts to advance in their understanding, knowledge and work on research impact. The WP8 team expects to update it on a six-monthly basis with the new and relevant information.

2.1. Landing Page

The landing page is the page users get first access to, through the ENLIGHT website, the future ENLIGHT R&I Observatory or other web platforms where the link to the repository is provided. In this landing page, users can see the repository navigation map, search for specific resources, find the latest uploads, and an introduction to the repository objectives, as presented below.

THE REPOSITORY

IMPACT is at the core of the mission of the [European University Alliance ENLIGHT](#) and, as such, one of its main objectives is to promote an impact-based culture within ENLIGHT Universities, including the promotion of a model of good practice of impact-directed management and the integration of impact across Higher Education, Research and Innovation activities.

*For that purpose, ENLIGHT research impact team is developing this **repository of international good practices on research impact assessment and measurement**. This initiative is part of the [ENLIGHT RISE project](#), funded by Horizon 20202 Science With and For Society, and aims at bringing together in a single place good practices of impact assessment and measurement, both in the context of ENLIGHT Universities and worldwide. More*

*specifically, this tool aims to **raise research impact awareness and literacy**, whilst fostering mutual learning and debate between ENLIGHT university academics, staff and external experts around research impact. It is supported by a set of complementary actions developed in the context of the ENLIGHT RISE project.*

*This repository should be seen as a **living tool** to be permanently nourished with the different guidelines, studies, analysis, tutorials and other reference sources allowing the ENLIGHT community and all interested experts to advance in their understanding, knowledge and work on research impact. Should you wish to help us in further developing the repository, please contact us [here](#).*

All sources included in this repository should be seen and understood in their specific academic, scientific, regional and historical context. There are no “one size fits for all” solutions and perfect methodologies, approaches, policy frameworks or strategic plans to promote research impact.

Do you need more information about our ENLIGHT impact-related work? Please contact us [here](#).

2.2. Understanding Research Impact

The screenshot shows the ENLIGHT repository interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'Search Good Practices on Research Impact...'. Below the search bar, there are navigation links: 'Understanding Research Impact', 'Policy Frameworks', 'Higher Education Institutions' Policies', 'Methodologies', and 'Our Research Impact Team'. The main content area features a dark blue header with the title 'UNDERSTANDING RESEARCH IMPACT' and a sub-header 'Research impact is often understood in two large dimensions: scientific/academic impact and socio-economic impact. The information and resources in this repository largely focus on the latter, whereby we define research impact as the effects of research in the real world.' To the right of the text is a photograph of a woman with glasses, wearing a blue shirt, sitting at a desk and holding a red pen to her chin, appearing to be in deep thought.

Impact is the changes we can see (demonstrate, measure, capture), beyond academia (in society, economy, environment) which happen because of our research (caused by, contributed to, attributable to). Impact may look and operate slightly differently across disciplines, and for fundamental versus applied research, but ultimately is about connecting academic research to changes in the real world.

The arena of impact is a minefield of terminology, with different countries, organisations, and funders adopting general or very specific vocabulary (e.g. knowledge mobilization, knowledge exchange, research uptake, valorization, etc.). Whatever the word or concept it is used, it is important to distinguish between what is the process (or the pathway to impact) and the intended or unintended effects (impact). For example, science communication or dissemination is not research impact but is a process which might contribute to the impact.

Whichever terminology or framework you use as reference, remember that impact may be big or small, local or global, instrumental (direct change) or conceptual (ideas, feelings), quantitative (products, jobs, revenues) or qualitative, positive or negative. There is no single type or area of impact nor a single type of impact pathway.

In this section, WP8 team shares different resources aimed at clarifying the concept of research impact: “What is Research Impact”?

UNDERSTANDING RESEARCH IMPACT

Research impact is often understood in two large dimensions: scientific/academic impact and socio-economic impact. The information and resources in this repository largely focus on the latter, whereby **we define research impact as the effects of research in the real world**. Impact is the changes we can see (demonstrate, measure, capture), beyond academia (in society, economy, environment) which happen because of our research (caused by, contributed to, attributable to). Impact may look and operate slightly differently across disciplines, and for fundamental versus applied research, but ultimately is about connecting academic research to changes in the real world.

The arena of impact is a minefield of terminology, with different countries, organizations, and funders adopting general or very specific vocabulary (e.g. knowledge mobilization, knowledge exchange, research uptake, valorization, etc.). Whatever the word or concept it is used, it is important to distinguish between what is the process (or the pathway to impact) and the intended or unintended effects (impact). For example, science communication or dissemination is not research impact but is a process which might contribute to the impact.

Whichever terminology or framework you use as reference, remember that impact may be big or small, local or global, instrumental (direct change) or conceptual (ideas, feelings), quantitative (products, jobs, revenues) or qualitative, positive or negative. There is no single type or area of impact nor a single type of impact pathway.

Online sources

- *What do we mean by “impact”?* Research to Action-The Global Guide to Research Impact <https://www.researchtoaction.org/2016/02/what-do-we-mean-by-impact>
- *Defining impact.* UK Research and Innovation <https://www.ukri.org/councils/esrc/impact-toolkit-for-economic-and-social-sciences/defining-impact/>
- *What is Research Impact?* NUI Galway <https://stories.nuigalway.ie/what-is-research-impact-/index.html>
- *Valorisation: researchers already do much more than they realise.* Rathenau Instituut <https://www.rathenau.nl/en/knowledge-policy/valorisation-researchers-already-do-much-more-they-realise>
- *What types of impact are there?* Fast Track Impact <https://www.fasttrackimpact.com/what-types-of-impact-are-there-subp>
- *Understand the outcomes and impacts that matter.* Matter of Focus <https://www.matter-of-focus.com/understand-the-outcomes-and-impacts-that-matter/>

Scholarly publications

- *The Co-produce Pathway to Impact.* David Phipps, Joanne Cummings, Debra Pepler, Wendy Craig, and Shelley Cardinal. Journal of Community Engagement Scholarship <http://jces.ua.edu/the-co-produced-pathway-to-impact-describes-knowledge-mobilization-processes/>
- *Maximising the impacts of your research: a handbook for social scientists.* LSE Public Policy Group http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/35758/1/Handbook_PDF_for_the_LSE_impact_blog_April_2011.pdf
- *What Is the Meaning of Impact in Relation to Research and Why Does It Matter? A View from Inside Academia.* Colin Chandler. Achieving Impact in Research. <https://methods.sagepub.com/book/achieving-impact-in-research/n1.xml>
- *Research impact. A guide to creating, capturing and evaluating the impact of your research.* Taylor & Francis Group. https://authorservices.taylorandfrancis.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Research_impact_ebook.pdf
- *Research impact: a narrative review.* Trisha Greenhalgh, James Raftery, Steve Hanney, Matthew Glover. BMC Medicine <https://bmcmmedicine.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12916-016-0620-8>
- *Conceptualizing the elements of research impact: towards semantic standards.* Brian Belcher, Janet Halliwell. Humanities & Social Sciences Communications. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-021-00854-2>

Video tutorials and training sources

- *Defining Research Impact.* Parthenos. <https://training.parthenos-project.eu/sample-page/intro-to-ri/research-impact/defining-research-impact/>
- *Understanding Research Impact.* Research Impact Academy. <https://researchimpactacademy.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Understanding-research-impact.pdf>

2.3. Policy Frameworks for Research Impact

POLICY FRAMEWORKS

The increased attention and support for research impact is driven by a number of 'external' factors including national policy, funders' requirements and research assessment.

SHARE

Governments, funding agencies and research organisations all over the globe increasingly seek to maximise societal and economic returns on investment in research by shaping research policy and practice.

Despite this common goal the approaches are often different. In some cases, researchers are expected to outline their plan for impact and receive funding on the promise of impact success; in other cases, large retrospective assessment exercises are set up making researchers eligible for future funding.

Many government agencies and research organisations are starting to use research impact assessment as a practical tool for decision-making in scientific strategy, demonstrating accountability to research funders, or even to allocate research resources.

In this section, the objective is to provide users with an overview of the main policy frameworks and the external drivers behind research impact: “What policies exist to promote research impact?”. The section includes general reflection resources, but also links to the different policy frameworks at the EU level, in European countries and worldwide.

POLICY FRAMEWORKS FOR RESEARCH IMPACT

The increased attention and support for research impact is driven by a number of 'external' factors including national policy, funders' requirements and research assessment. Governments, funding agencies and research organisations all over the globe increasingly seek to maximise societal and economic returns on investment in research by shaping research policy and practice.

Despite this common goal the approaches are often different. In some cases, researchers are expected to outline their plan for impact and receive funding on the promise of impact success; in other cases, large retrospective assessment exercises are set up making researchers eligible for future funding. Many government agencies and research organisations are starting to use research impact assessment as a practical tool for decision-making in scientific strategy, demonstrating accountability to research funders, or even to allocate research resources.

General Reflections

- *Unique, But Still Best Practice? The Research Excellence Framework (Ref) from an International Perspective.* Gunnar Sivertsen. Palgrave Communications.
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3020671
- *How do organisations implement research impact assessment (RIA) principles and good practice? A narrative review and exploratory study of four international research funding and administrative organisations.* Adam Kamenetzky, Saba Hinrichs-Krapels. Health Research Policy and Systems.
<https://health-policy-systems.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12961-019-0515-1>

European Framework

In the European Union, evaluations serve to create a crucial evidence base for the implementation of research and innovation programmes and are legally required for all framework programmes. Past programmes have been evaluated, the current programmes are being monitored and put forward the expectation that EU-funded research maximises impact.

- *Impact assessment of the Horizon Europe programme*
https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/evaluation-impact-assessment-and-monitoring/horizon-europe_en
- *Monitoring the impact of EU Framework Programmes.*
<https://op.europa.eu/es/publication-detail/-/publication/cbb7ce39-d66d-11e8-9424-01aa75ed71a1>
- *How to approach the Horizon Europe Impact section for Collaborative Projects.* Enspire.science
<https://enspire.science/how-to-approach-the-horizon-europe-impact-section-for-collaborative-projects/>

European Countries

- **Norway:** [Recent Research and Innovation Evaluations in Norway](#)
- **Poland:** [Toward an excellence-based research funding system: Evidence from Poland.](#) Emmanuel Kulczycki, Marcin Korzen, Przemyslaw Korytkowski. Journal of Informetrics.
- **Poland:** [Poland's impact evaluation gets lost in translation](#)
- **Sweden:** [Research Quality Evaluation in Sweden – FOKUS](#)
<https://www.vr.se/english/analysis/reports/our-reports/2015-06-25-research-quality-evaluation-in-sweden---fokus.html>
- **The Netherlands:** [Strategy Evaluation Protocol \(SEP\) for research](#)
- **United Kingdom:** [Research Excellence Framework](#)

Worldwide

- **Australia:** [Engagement and Impact Assessment](#)
- **Canada:** [Framework and Indicators for measuring returns on investment in Health Research](#)
- **Hong Kong:** [Research Assessment Exercise](#)
- **Singapore:** [Research Assessment in Singaporean Higher Education.](#) Lesley Vidovich. International Education Journal: Comparative Perspectives.
- **USA:** [National Science Foundation Broader Impacts](#)

2.4. Higher Education Policies for Research Impact

In the same way that the size, structure, governance and focus of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) vary considerably across Europe and beyond, the approach taken by HEIs to Research Impact Policy and how or even if it is incorporated into an overall Institutional Policy Framework is equally diverse.

Many HEIs do not have a standalone Research Impact Policy but do have a commitment to supporting and achieving impactful research, which is embedded in a wider Institutional Strategy, Institutional Research and Innovation Strategy or more specifically a school/faculty strategy.

The EARMA Impact Strategy Survey (2019-2020) found that of the HEI respondents, 27% had a standalone Research Impact Strategy while for 50%, commitment to Research Impact was embedded in a broader institutional strategy. These results are consistent with a 2021 Landscaping Survey carried out by ENLIGHT RISE of the 9 ENLIGHT Universities which found that just one of the partner universities had a standalone Research Impact Policy and four had embedded a commitment to research impact into a broader institutional strategy.

Certainly, the most comprehensive approach would be the adoption at HEIs of specific Research Impact Policy that underpins a strategic plan and is effected by an implementation plan that is adequately and appropriately resourced. However, this comprehensive approach is not a prerequisite to achieving, recording and assessing impactful research but the support of institutional structures, policies and processes certainly is.

A number of resources are available for HEIs to self-assess their existing structure to determine how 'healthy' they are in terms of supporting and generating impact and this is a good first step in identifying way to improve.

In this section of the repository, a general overview of the different approaches taken by Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to research impact is provided. The section aims to provide the resources to help answer the question: "What are HEIs doing to promote research impact?". The section includes general reflection resources, as well as links to HEIs research impact policies, being standalone or embedded in a wider institutional strategy. Additionally, it provides resources for HEIs to self-assess how "healthy" they are in terms of supporting and generating impact.

HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS' POLICIES FOR RESEARCH IMPACT

In the same way that the size, structure, governance and focus of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) vary considerably across Europe and beyond, the approach taken by HEIs to Research Impact Policy and how or even if it is incorporated into an overall Institutional Policy Framework is equally diverse.

Many HEIs do not have a standalone Research Impact Policy but do have a commitment to supporting and achieving impactful research, which is embedded in a wider Institutional Strategy, Institutional Research and Innovation Strategy or more specifically a school/faculty strategy.

The EARMA Impact Strategy Survey (2019-2020) found that of the HEI respondents, 27% had a standalone Research Impact Strategy while for 50%, commitment to Research Impact was embedded in a broader institutional strategy. These results are consistent with a 2021 Landscaping Survey carried out by ENLIGHT RISE of the 9 ENLIGHT Universities which found that just one of the partner universities had a standalone Research Impact Policy and four had embedded a commitment to research impact into a broader institutional strategy.

Certainly, the most comprehensive approach would be the adoption at HEIs of specific Research Impact Policy that underpins a strategic plan and is effected by an implementation plan that is adequately and appropriately resourced. However, this comprehensive approach is not a prerequisite to achieving, recording and assessing impactful research but the support of institutional structures, policies and processes certainly is.

A number of resources are available for HEIs to self-assess their existing structure to determine how 'healthy' they are in terms of supporting and generating impact and this is a good first step in identifying way to improve.

General Reflections

- *Diversity of Institutional Support for Research Impact Implementation*. W. Nicol Keith, Xinzi Yu and Rose-Marie Barbeau.
<https://www.budrich-journals.de/index.php/zdfm/article/download/32671/28104>
- *Building Research Capacity for Impact in Applied Health Services Research Partnerships Comment on "Experience of Health Leadership in Partnering With University-Based Researchers in Canada – A Call to "Re-imagine" Research"*. Jo Cooke.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7947663/>
- *How universities influence societal impact practices: Academics' sense-making of organizational impact strategies*. Stefan P L de Jong and Corina Balaban.
<https://academic.oup.com/spp/advance-article/doi/10.1093/scipol/scac012/6552261>

Standalone HEIs Research Impact Related Policies

- Ghent University (ENLIGHT. Belgium)
<https://www.uqent.be/en/research/science-society/impact/soc-impact.htm>
- The University of Manchester (United Kingdom)
<https://www.socialresponsibility.manchester.ac.uk>
- University of Deusto (Spain)
<https://www.deusto.es/cs/Satellite/deustoresearch/en/home/dissemination-and-transfer>
- Stellenbosch University (South Africa)
<http://www.sun.ac.za/si/en-za/Pages/about.aspx>

Embedded HEIs Research Impact Related Policies

- NUI Galway (ENLIGHT. Ireland)
<https://www.nuigalway.ie/researchcommunityportal/researchimpact/>
- University of Groningen (ENLIGHT. The Netherlands)
<https://www.ruq.nl/about-ua/policy-and-strategy/strategic-plan/strategisch-plan-enq-2021.pdf>
- University of the Basque Country (ENLIGHT. Spain)
<https://www.ehu.es/en/web/iraunkortasuna/ehuagenda-2030>
- University of Southern Denmark (Denmark)
https://www.sdu.dk/en/om_sdu/sdus_profil/strategi
- University of Gothenburg (Sweden)
<https://www.qu.se/en/about-the-university/vision-and-values/vision-2021-2030-a-university-for-the-world>
- Erasmus University Rotterdam (The Netherlands)
<https://www.eur.nl/en/about-eur/strategy-2024>
- The University of Melbourne (Australia)
<https://about.unimelb.edu.au/strategy/advancing-melbourne>
- York University (Canada)
<https://www.yorku.ca/uap2020-25/>
- University of Otago (New Zealand)

<https://www.otago.ac.nz/about/social-responsibility/>

- Carnegie Mellon University (USA)

<https://www.cmu.edu/strategic-plan/societal-impact/index.html>

Other Organisations' Research Impact Related Policies

- Universities Canada (Canada)

<https://www.univcan.ca/priorities/social-impact/>

Examples of Institutional Research Literacy Assessment

- Institutional Healthcheck Workbook. Julie Bailey and David Phipps.

<https://www.emeraldgrouppublishing.com/sites/default/files/2020-06/Institutional%20Healthcheck%20Workbook%20Final.pdf>

- Impact Strategy Survey (2019-2020)_ Bettina Uhrig and Andrew Jackson. EARMA Policy and Representation Committee.

<https://earma.org/media/documents/impact-strategy-survey.pdf>

- Assessment of Institutional Support and Staff Awareness of Research Impact Across ACCOMPLISSH Partner Institutions

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b3007a0c&applied=PPGMS>

2.5. Methodologies for Research Impact

This section presents methodologies for both the planning of and the assessment of research impact with focus being beyond the academic environment. As research even within specific disciplines is vastly varied so too are the benefits or perceived benefits of these efforts which immediately poses a dilemma in planning for, but also in the comprehensive assessment of research impact. This dilemma has given rise to different approaches for measuring and assessment of research impact.

Planning for research impact increases the likelihood of the research making a positive difference in the world. Resources for impact planning help researchers to identify who in society will likely benefit from the research that they are undertaking, decide how researchers can connect with the right people to ensure that the impacts are achieved, engage these stakeholders in the research process and relay to others about the potential impact.

Concerning the assessment or evaluation of research impact, much have been written about and five broad types of research impact evaluation are commonly proposed (e.g. Reed et al., 2021):

- Systems analysis methods: pathways to impact, establishment of causation links, etc.
- Textual, oral and arts-based methods: case studies, interviews, testimonials, etc.
- Indicator-based approaches: focus on indicators or any type demonstration of impact from process of change.
- Evidence synthesis approaches: mixed evaluation methods to establish cause and effect.

This section presents methodologies for both the planning of and the assessment of research impact. It also includes resources and provides examples of impactful research case studies. This section aims to answer the question: How can I plan, assess and measure research impact?

METHODOLOGIES FOR RESEARCH IMPACT

As funders increasingly require evidence of the benefit of the research that they have supported, interest grows in methodologies to best assess these benefits and plan to ensure that they are achieved.

This section presents methodologies for both the planning and the assessment of research impact with focus being beyond the academic environment. As research even within specific disciplines is vastly varied so too are the benefits or perceived benefits of these efforts which immediately poses a dilemma in planning for, but also in the comprehensive assessment of research impact. This dilemma has given rise to different approaches for measuring and assessment of research impact.

Planning for research impact increases the likelihood of the research making a positive difference in the world. Resources for impact planning help researchers to identify who in society will likely benefit from the research that they are undertaking, decide how researchers can connect with the right people to ensure that the impacts are achieved, engage these stakeholders in the research process and relay to others about the potential impact.

Concerning the assessment or evaluation of research impact, much have been written about and five broad types of research impact evaluation are commonly proposed (e.g. Reed et al., 2021):

- *Systems analysis methods*: pathways to impact, establishment of causation links, etc.
- *Textual, oral and arts-based methods*: case studies, interviews, testimonials, etc.

- *Indicator-based approaches*: focus on indicators or any type demonstration of impact from process of change.
- *Evidence synthesis approaches*: mixed evaluation methods to establish cause and effect.

Impact toolkits

- o NUI Galway Research Impact Toolkit
- o <https://stories.nuigalway.ie/research-impact-toolkit/index.html>
- o Ghent University impact toolkit for researchers
<https://www.ugent.be/intranet/en/research/soc-value>
- o Broader Impacts Toolkit. ARIS: Advancing Research Impact in Society
<https://researchinsociety.org/resources/>
- o Europeana Impact Playbook
<https://pro.europeana.eu/page/europeana-impact-playbook>
- o Impact Resources. Vertigo Ventures
<https://www.vertigoventures.com/resources/>
- o Knowledge Translation Tools. Melanie Barwick Consulting: Building Research Impact
<https://melaniebarwick.com/knowledge-translation-tools/>
- o LSE Impact Blog: a platform for understanding and increasing the impact of academic research
<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/>
- o Research Impact Canada: Turning Research into Action
<https://researchimpact.ca>
- o Research to Action: The Global Guide to Research Impact
<https://www.researchtoaction.org>
- o RRI Toolkit
<https://rri-tools.eu>
- o UCD Research Impact Toolkit
<https://www.ucd.ie/impacttoolkit/>

Impact planning

- o NUI Galway Research Impact Toolkit: Plan
<https://stories.nuigalway.ie/plan/index.html>
- o Engaged Research Planning for Impact (Irish Universities Association (IUA) [Campus Engage](https://www.campusengage.ie))
https://www.campusengage.ie/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Campus_Engage_Impact_Framework_May_2018_Web.pdf
- o Fast Track Impact Planning Template (Professor Mark Reed, Newcastle University)
<https://www.fasttrackimpact.com/post/2019/03/18/research-impact-planning>
- o Impact Literacy Workbook: Helping you demonstrate the provable effects of your research in the real world
<https://www.emeraldgrouppublishing.com/sites/default/files/2020-06/Impact%20Literacy%20Workbook%20Final.pdf>
- o Stakeholder Analysis Template (Professor Mark Reed, Newcastle University)
<https://www.fasttrackimpact.com/post/2019/03/11/how-to-do-stakeholder-analysis>
- o Supporting PIs to Plan for Research Impact (Principal Investigator Impact, CÚRAM (Research Centre for Medical Devices))
<http://www.piimpact.com/>
- o Theory of Change (Center for Theory of Change)
<https://www.theoryofchange.org/what-is-theory-of-change/>
- o UCD Research Impact Toolkit: Impact Planning Canvas
<https://www.ucd.ie/impacttoolkit/plan/ucdimpactplanningcanvas/>

Impact measurement and assessment

- o Sustainable Development Goals Indicators

<https://unstats.un.org/sdgs>

- SDG Impact Assessment Tool (Gothenburg Centre for Sustainable Development)
<https://sdgimpactassessmenttool.org/en-gb>
- Horizon Europe Key Impact Pathways
https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/evaluation-impact-assessment-and-monitoring/horizon-europe_en#monitoring-horizon-europe
- UK Research Excellence Framework
<https://www.ref.ac.uk/>
- Australia's National Science Agency Impact Evaluation Guide
<https://www.csiro.au/en/about/Corporate-governance/Ensuring-our-impact>
- San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)
<https://sfдора.org>
- The Leiden Manifesto for research metrics (Diana Hicks, Paul Wouters, Ludo Waltman, Sarah de Rikcke, Ismael Rafolds)
<https://www.nature.com/articles/520429a>
- IRIS Catalog of metrics
<https://iris.thegiin.org/metrics/>
- Next generation metrics: Responsible metrics and evaluation for open science
<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/b858d952-0a19-11e7-8a35-01aa75ed71a1>
- Altmeter for Researchers
<https://www.altmetric.com/audience/researchers/>
- ISRIA statement: ten-point guidelines for an effective process of research impact assessment
<https://health-policy-systems.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12961-018-0281-5>
- NUI Galway Research Impact Toolkit – Monitor
<https://stories.nuigalway.ie/monitor/index.html>
- Hunter Medical Research Institute: Research Impact Assessment
<https://hmri.org.au/FAIT>
- Methods for analyzing collaboration and societal impact (The Swedish Research Council)
https://www.vr.se/download/18.47291b121711f04ce6eb99/1587033832314/Metoder%20for%20att%20analysera%20samverkan%20och%20samhallspaverkan_VR_2020.pdf
- Impact Evaluation – Better Evaluation
https://www.betterevaluation.org/en/themes/impact_evaluation

Impactful research case studies

- Horizon Results Platform
<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>
- UK Research Excellence Framework – Case Studies
<https://impact.ref.ac.uk/casestudies/>
- Australian Research Council Impact Studies
<https://dataportal.arc.gov.au/EI/Web/impact/ImpactStudies>
- Social Impact Open Repository (SIOR)
<https://www.ub.edu/sior/register.php>
- Success stories about the impact of Ghent University research
<https://www.ugent.be/en/research/science-society/impact/impact-success.htm>
- Impact of EU-funded research impact at Ghent University (ENLIGHT. Ghent University)
<https://www.ugent.be/en/research/science-society/impact/impact-eu.htm>
- NUI Galway Research Impact Case Studies (ENLIGHT. NUI Galway)
<https://stories.nuigalway.ie/research-impact-toolkit/index.html>
- University College Dublin – Impact Case Studies

<https://www.ucd.ie/research/impact/casestudies/>

- Imperial College London – Case Studies
<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/research-and-innovation/impact/>
- University of Cambridge – Case Studies Worldwide Mapping
<https://impactmap.cam.ac.uk>

Other specific impact pathway approaches

- Creating the conditions for uptake in higher education partnerships for sustainable development. VLIR-UOS
<https://cdn.vliruos.be/vliruos/210126-VLIRUOS-UPTAKE-A4brochure.pdf>
- Evidence-informed policy making. European Commission
https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/evidence-informed-policy-making_en
- Impacttool. Erasmus+ Dutch National Agencies Erasmus+
<https://www.erasmusplus.nl/en/impacttool-mobility>
- Planning your public engagement. Wellcome Trust
<https://wellcome.org/grant-funding/guidance/planning-your-public-engagement>
- Public Engagement Evaluation Toolkit. Queen Mary University of London
<https://www.qmul.ac.uk/publicengagement/goodpractice/evaluation-toolkit/>
- Resources for high quality engagement. UK National Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement
<https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/resources>

2.6. Our Research Impact Team

ENLIGHT

Search Good Practices on Research Impact...

THE REPOSITORY

Understanding Research Impact Policy Frameworks Higher Education Institutions' Policies Methodologies **Our Research Impact Team**

back to home

OUR RESEARCH IMPACT TEAM

SHARE

Impact is in itself a field of research that is growing in importance and relevance worldwide. Accompanying the increasing number of organisations that are analyzing their impact and the impact of their activities on society, there is a growing number of researchers, experts and practitioners on impact policy, measurement, assessment, communication and management.

The present repository focuses on the impact generated by the research activity, but impact expertise extends well beyond the Higher Education domain and covers also other fields, such as impact of economic activities or environmental impact assessments. We are of the view that independently of the focus of the impact assessment exercise, there are important insights that can be taken from the different methodological approaches and tools used in the different fields of action.

Below you can find the details on how to reach the ENLIGHT Research Impact coordination team, as well as your point of contact on research impact at different ENLIGHT Universities. The objective is to complete this list with external experts' contacts.

Would you like to be part of our list of experts?

Please [contact us here](#).

In this section users can find the details on how to reach the ENLIGHT Research Impact coordination team, as well as the points of contact on research impact at different ENLIGHT Universities. The objective is to complete this list with external experts' contacts in the future. The section aims at answering the question: "Who can I contact for support?".

OUR RESEARCH IMPACT TEAM

Impact is in itself a field of research that is growing in importance and relevance worldwide. Accompanying the increasing number of organizations that are analyzing their impact and the impact of their activities on society, there is a growing number of researchers, experts and practitioners on impact policy, measurement, assessment, communication and management.

The present repository focuses on the impact generated by the research activity, but impact expertise extends well beyond the Higher Education domain and covers also other fields, such as impact of economic activities or environmental impact assessments. We are of the view that independently of the focus of the impact assessment exercise, there are important insights that can be taken from the different methodological approaches and tools used in the different fields of action.

Below you can find the details on how to reach the ENLIGHT Research Impact coordination team, as well as your point of contact on research impact at different ENLIGHT Universities. The objective is to complete this list with external experts' contacts.

Would you like to be part of our list of experts? Please contact us [here](#).

ENLIGHT Research Impact Coordination Team

Igor Campillo

[University of the Basque Country. Euskampus Fundazioa](#)

Esther De Smet

[Ghent University. Research Department – Policy and Quality Enhancement Unit](#)

Louise Hannon

[NUI Galway. Research Office.](#)

Glória Nunes Rodrigues

[University of the Basque Country. Euskampus Fundazioa](#)

impact.enlight@ehu.es

ENLIGHT Universities

University of Groningen

Shaya Abdolazadeh

[Research Intelligence Services](#)

rise@rug.nl

Ana Ranitović

[Research Intelligence Services](#)

rise@rug.nl

Uppsala University

Björn Nyström

[Unit for Global Partnerships](#)

Bjorn.nystrom@uu.se

3. THE WEB-BASED TOOL

The web-based tool acting as repository of good practices on research impact was published on 19 August 2022 at this link impact.enlight-eu.org.

It is accessible through the ENLIGHT website, at the [Research & Innovation](#) tab. In the future it will also be accessible through the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory.

It will be disseminated through ENLIGHT communication tools and the different ENLIGHT Universities dissemination means, in alignment with WP8 task 8.1.1. specific objective of *“ensuring wide internal dissemination of best international practices on R&I impact assessment”*. It will be introduced to the newly established FOREU2 Impact thematic group and disseminated at the HEI Impact Conference organized in the framework of WP6 – Impact of the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ project, which is planned to take place on 29-31 March 2023 in Bilbao.

As previously mentioned, the repository is open to the overall public and should be seen as a **living tool** to be permanently nourished with the different guidelines, studies, analysis, tutorials and other reference sources allowing the ENLIGHT community and all interested experts to advance in their understanding, knowledge and work on research impact. It will be updated on a six-monthly basis with the latest relevant resources identified by the ENLIGHT Research Impact team.